

EFFECT OF ANISOTROPY IN FIBRE BUNDLE SPACING ON MACROVOID FORMATION IN VISCOUS-FLUID IMPREGNATION TO WOVEN GLASS FIBRE

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ABSTRACT

We conduct a series of experiments on impregnation of viscous fluid into woven fibre bundles placed between parallel plates to simulate resin impregnation near the substrates in VARTM method. This study particularly focuses on the impact of anisotropy in fibre bundle spacing on macrovoids formation. It is found that flow near the flow front changes by varying anisotropy in fibre bundle spacing. We reveal that aspect ratio of the space among fibre bundle dramatically affects macrovoid formation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) is a composite material manufactured by impregnating fluid, such as epoxy or phenolic resin, into fibre bundles. FRP exhibits high strength and stiffness, together with low weight and ease of processing. Due to its superior specific strength compared to metals, FRP has been widely used as a substitute for metallic materials in various applications, including aerospace components and automotive bodies. Among the forming techniques for FRP, one notable method is Liquid Composite Molding (LCM). One prominent example is the VARTM (Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding) method, which accelerates resin impregnation by using vacuum pump, has numerous advantages and ability to mold materials and manufacture in any type of shape with a wide range of spatial scales with low cost. However, it also has the disadvantage that entrapments of gas remained in the mold are prone to occur due to unintended insufficient impregnation during the resin flow. Entrapped gas, or void, can cause stress concentration and significantly decrease the trustworthiness of manufactured composites. To maintain quality of composite materials, it is essential to elucidate the conditions for void formation and suppression. Two types of voids have been defined: microvoids which form within fibre bundles, and macrovoids which form between fibre bundles [1]. This study focuses on the latter, as it has more significant impact on tensile and compressive strength of materials [2]. Extensive research has been conducted on the behavior of fluid impregnation within fibre bundles in the VARTM process. Total volume of residual voids varies with some factors such as the capillary number (Ca), a dimensionless number representing the characteristic velocity of fluid, and wettability [3,4].

$$Ca = \frac{\mu U}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where μ , σ , and U , represent the viscosity, the surface tension, and the impregnation velocity of the test fluid, respectively. When Ca is small—that is, when capillary forces dominate—the test fluid preferentially flows between the fibre tows and gradually fills the interior of each tow. In this regime,

macrovoids are prone to form between fibre bundles. Conversely, when Ca is large, the formation of macrovoids is suppressed; however, micro-voids tend to form within the fibre bundles with higher probability. Although the optimal capillary number (Ca) depends on multiple factors, including the structure of fibre bundles and is therefore difficult to determine uniquely, a value of $Ca \approx 10^{-3}$ is regarded as effective threshold for suppressing void formation across various conditions [5,6]. Furthermore, it has been experimentally demonstrated that increasing the contact angle at the solid-liquid interface—i.e., reducing wettability—suppresses deformation of the flow front, thus reducing macrovoid formation even under low Ca conditions [7,8]. It has also revealed that wettability has a significant influence on flow patterns within porous media, particularly on void geometry and residual void content through X-ray 3D scanning of fluid displacement in carbon fibre preforms [8]. This study targets on woven fibre bundles placed between parallel plates to simulate resin impregnation near the substrates in the VARTM method, and particularly focuses on the impact of anisotropy in fibre bundle spacing on the viscous fluid impregnation dynamics.

2 EXPERIMENTS

The experimental apparatus used in this study is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1. To prepare a mold, we settle the single-layer woven glass fibre mat between acrylic flat plates on both sides, which are fixed by jigs made of SUS. To prevent gas-liquid leakage into or out of the mold, an O-ring is installed between each acrylic plate and the jig. The inlet of the mold is connected to a reservoir of test liquid, and the outlet is connected to a vacuum pump (DA-60D, ULVAC, Inc., Japan) to create a pressure difference within the mold, each via rubber tubes. The pressure difference within the mold is adjusted using two regulators (IRV 10-C08L, SMC, Corp., Japan) connected between the outlet of the mold and the vacuum pump, and measured with a pressure meter (MT300-D01, Yokogawa Test & Measurement Corporation, Japan). 350-cSt silicone oil (KF-96-350 CS, Shin-Etsu Chemical Co., Ltd., Japan) is employed as test liquid, and fluorescent particles are mixed in the liquid as tracers for visualization. Light emitting diode (LED) (AITEC SYSTEM, Co., LTD., Japan) is placed to visualize the flow front of the impregnating liquid with white light. Additionally, a continuous laser light of 532 nm in wavelength is irradiated at the imaging area through a half-mirror to excite the fluorescent particles to visualize particle behavior in the liquid. The images of the impregnation process are recorded by using charge-coupled device (CCD) camera (C9300 – 221, Hamamatsu Photonics, K.K., Japan) of 640 x 480 pixel at 20 fps from the underside of the mold with 60 mm lens (Micro-Nikkor 60mm f/2.8D, Nikon, Inc., Japan). To prevent the CCD camera from receiving the laser light, a short-pass filter is placed between the CCD camera and the half mirror. Before conducting each experiment, the sealed container containing the test liquid is subjected to ultrasonic vibration for one hour to obtain a uniformly dispersed mixture of particles. Also, the test liquid is degassed under -90 kPa for at least three hours to remove residual air within the liquid. Figure 2 shows the woven glass fibre mats (Featherfield, K.K., Japan) with different anisotropies in fibre bundle spacing used in this study. Fibre bundles aligned in the main flow direction are referred to as warp, while those oriented in the spanwise direction are referred to as weft. The aspect ratios of the gaps, where neither warp nor weft fibre bundles are present, are varied as (a) 1:1, (b) 1:3, and (c) 3:1. The fibre mat used in each experiment consisted of fibres with a diameter of 17 μm .

The density per area is (a) 550 g/m^2 , and (b) and (c) 462 g/m^2 . The test liquid is silicone oil as aforementioned, whose kinematic viscosity, density, and surface tension are 350 mm^2/s , 967.4 g/m^3 , 21.1 mN/m respectively. All experiments are conducted under constant conditions at a room temperature of 22 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 1: Experimental apparatus for visualizing impregnation process into woven glass fibre mats in mold.

Figure 2: Three types of woven glass fibre mats with anisotropy in fibre bundle spacing. Aspect ratio of each gaps, $L_{weft} : L_{warp}$, is (a) 1:1 (b) 1:3 (c) 3:1.

3 RESULTS&DISCUSSION

Figure 3 shows a representative example of impregnation behavior. The left three columns represent experimental results, and the rightmost column shows results of numerical simulation [9]. The experimental results include instantaneous fields near the flow front at two representative time points ($t - t_0 = 0$ [s], 10 [s]) and pathline images obtained by integrating instantaneous fields over these time intervals. Under all conditions, the warp fibre bundles in the upper left and lower right crimp are positioned in the foreground (from the viewing side), and the same applies to the weft fibre bundles in the upper right and lower left crimp. This study replicates the flow front behavior in the snap-off process, as previously observed by simulation [7] and by experiments [7,10]. Snap-off refers to a phenomenon in which advancing flow front moves around the gap, resulting in spontaneous filling of the weft fibre at the downstream side of the gap and disconnection of the non-wetting phase [11]. The flow behavior near the flow front is visualized by tracking fluorescent particles. Under each condition, at the upstream side of the gap, the liquid near the flow front moves around the gap, resulting in a flow velocity component in the z -axis direction at both the upper and lower sides. As impregnation progresses, the liquid flows along the warp fibre bundles in the lower-right crimp (as indicated as (iii)), resulting in dominant flow velocity component in the x -axis direction. In contrast, in the upper-right crimp (i), the liquid permeates along the weft fibre at the downstream side of the gap (ii), resulting in a flow velocity component in the z -axis direction. This phenomenon is particularly noticeable in Panel (c). These results are well reproduced by the present numerical simulation (rightmost column in Fig. 3) for each gap geometry. The liquid motion along the weft fibres in the downstream side of the gap (ii) enhances the curvature of the flow front near the boundary between the gap and weft fibre bundle (as shown at the right edge of the gap), thereby increasing the Laplace pressure. As a result, it suppresses macrovoid formation by inducing detachment of the interface at the warp fibre edge in the gap. This tendency is particularly pronounced under the condition of a 3:1 aspect ratio gap (Panel (c)), supporting the results by Matsuzaki et al. [12], which showed that macrovoid formation is less likely in fibre mats with lower $L_{\text{weft}}/L_{\text{warp}}$. It is important to note that the weft and warp fibre bundles have different thicknesses in their study.

Figure 3: Representative examples of impregnation behavior under each gap aspect ratio: (a) 1:1, (b) 1:3, and (c) 3:1. The left three columns represent experimental results, while the rightmost column shows numerical results.

Figure 4 shows an instantaneous field of the observation region captured by the CCD camera. A dashed line in the figure indicates the evaluation line defined for evaluating the representative impregnation velocity of the liquid. The left panel shows the raw image data, while the right panel displays the velocity field obtained via PIV analysis, overlaid on the raw image. PIV data are processed using filter based on the discrete cosine transform (DCT) [13]. The impregnation velocity of the test liquid is evaluated using the velocity data obtained from the PIV. We define the representative impregnation velocity $\overline{U}_{x,20s}$ as the time-averaged x-direction velocity along the inspection line over 20-second interval, selected after the flow front has sufficiently advanced and the flow has stabilized. The same evaluation method is applied under all aspect ratio conditions.

Figure 4: Instantaneous field of observation region with dashed evaluation line used for evaluating $\overline{U}_{x,20s}$. The left panel shows the raw image data, while the right panel displays the velocity field obtained from the PIV, visualized using the filter based on DCT.

Figure 5 shows instantaneous field immediately after snap-off for each aspect ratio condition. The left two columns represent experimental results, and the rightmost column shows results by the numerical simulation [9]. The first column of experimental results illustrates the raw instantaneous field overlaid with a schematic of the local fibre orientation and highlighted gas-liquid interfaces. The closed interfaces entrapped in the gap region are marked in green, while the leading flow front is highlighted in pink. The second column of experimental results displays a magnified view of the velocity vector field obtained by the PIV (with DCT filter) focusing on the snap-off region, with the gas-liquid interfaces emphasized in the same color scheme. The color distribution in the vector field is determined by the x-direction velocity normalized by the representative impregnation velocity $\overline{U}_{x,20s}$ defined above. The same image processing and analysis procedure is applied to all aspect ratio conditions (a) 1:1, (b) 1:3, and (c) 3:1. Regarding the velocity field, particularly in conditions (a) and (c), large velocity vectors are observed along the gas-liquid interfaces. Along the interface highlighted in green, positive velocities appear both above and below a negative velocity region located near the snap-off region. In contrast, along the interface highlighted in pink, the velocity near the snap-off region is positive, while negative velocities are observed above and below it. This velocity distribution is attributed to the rapid deformation of the gas-liquid interface caused by snap-off, which draws in the surrounding liquid and leads to the expansion of the constriction between gas-liquid interfaces in the x-direction. Although a similar tendency is observed under the condition of a 1:3 aspect ratio gap (Panel (b)), no prominent velocity distribution appears in any region. The tendency for the constricted region to exhibit an opposite velocity to that of upper and lower regions is also well reproduced by the present numerical simulations for each gap shape. In the presentation, we also incorporate experimentally obtained shear fields into

our discussion, alongside the results of numerical results.

Figure 5: Velocity fields immediately after snap-off for each aspect ratio: (a) 1:1, (b) 1:3, and (c) 3:1. The left two columns show the experimental results, and the rightmost column shows the numerical simulation results. The left column presents raw image data, while the center column displays a magnified view of velocity field obtained via the PIV. In both experimental columns, a schematic of the local fibre orientation and highlighted gas-liquid interfaces are overlaid.

3 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study investigates the impregnation behavior of a viscous fluid into woven fibre bundles placed between parallel plates, with particular focus on the impact of the anisotropy in fibre bundle spacing influences the impregnation behavior. We prepared three kinds of fibre mats with different gap aspect ratio: 1:1, 1:3, and 3:1. We mixed fluorescent tracer particles into test liquid to examine impregnation behavior. For each aspect ratio condition, comparisons between experimentally obtained pathline and velocity fields predicted by numerical simulations showed good agreement in overall trends. The results demonstrated that the magnitude of spanwise velocity along weft fibres in the downstream of the gap has a significant impact on macrovoid formation in this system.

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